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Innovation linkages at the global level

Innovation linkages have decreased by an average of 1.09% between 2013 and 2022 for the countries considered.

The variable "innovation linkages" refers to the degree of connection and collaboration among various actors in a country's or region's innovation system. This variable measures how effectively businesses, universities, research centers, and other institutions work together to develop, disseminate, and apply new ideas and technologies. Innovation linkages are fundamental because they promote the exchange of knowledge, resources, and skills, which are essential for stimulating innovation and enhancing economic competitiveness. Innovation linkages include various forms of collaboration, such as public-private partnerships, research consortia, business networks, and technology transfer programs. These connections can occur at the national, regional, or international level, involving not only the private and public sectors but also non-governmental organizations and other entities within civil society. A high level of innovation linkages indicates a well-integrated innovation ecosystem where different actors can collaborate effectively, share information and resources, and work toward common technological and innovative development goals. Conversely, a low level of innovation linkages suggests a fragmented system where interactions among various actors are limited, thereby hindering the flow of ideas and the adoption of new technologies. This variable is often used as an indicator of a country's potential to develop and commercialize innovations. A system with strong innovation linkages is more likely to produce successful innovations and sustain long-term economic growth, as it facilitates the sharing of risks, costs, and expertise among the participants in the innovation system.

Innovation linkages globally in 2022. The analysis of innovation linkages data in 2022 shows significant variation among countries in their ability to create and maintain effective connections among different actors in the innovation system. At the top of the ranking is Israel, with a score of 78.4, significantly higher than any other country. This result is not surprising, considering the high level of collaboration between the public sector, universities, research centers, and industry that characterizes the country. Israel is renowned for its highly connected innovation ecosystem, fueled by a robust entrepreneurial culture and strong government support, which together promote a dense network of partnerships that extend internationally. Sweden, with a score of 68.3, and Finland, with 66.4, follow at a distance but still demonstrate a high capacity for linkages within their innovation systems. Both Nordic countries have historically invested in research infrastructures and advanced education policies, facilitating collaboration between public and private entities. These countries benefit from stable governance and a high level of social trust, elements that facilitate cooperation and shared innovation. The United States, with a score of 66, is another example of a country with strong innovation linkages. The combination of world-class universities, a dynamic private sector, and availability of venture capital makes the United States a global leader in innovation. However, compared to other top-ranking countries like Israel, the size and complexity of the U.S. system can

pose challenges in maintaining a uniform level of connections across the country. Switzerland, with a score of 64.3, reflects its long tradition of scientific excellence and strong cooperation between the public and private sectors. Its academic and research institutions are among the best in the world, and interaction with industry is facilitated by a favorable regulatory environment and a well-established entrepreneurial culture. Canada and Iceland, both with a score of 59.8, represent countries with solid innovation ecosystems, although not at the level of leading nations. In Canada, collaboration between universities and industries, particularly in emerging technologies and life sciences, is one of the driving forces behind its innovation linkages. Iceland, despite its small size, has developed a well-connected innovation network, especially in the energy and technology sectors, facilitated by government policies that promote research and development. In the group of countries with moderate scores, we find Austria, Belgium, and Singapore, with scores of 57.5, 55.9, and 54.3, respectively. These countries show a good level of linkage within their innovation systems, although there is room for improvement. For example, Singapore, despite being a global technology and financial hub, could benefit from greater integration between its excellent research infrastructure and industry to further strengthen its innovation linkages. Moving on to countries like the United Kingdom (52) and Germany (52.2), which have scores slightly above 50, we notice that despite their strong traditions of research and development, there are challenges in maintaining uniform cohesion across the various sectors of innovation. In particular, the United Kingdom, with its recent exit from the European Union, may face new challenges in maintaining its innovation linkages internationally. Germany, despite its powerful manufacturing industry, may need further efforts to better integrate its small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) into the national innovation system. Further down the ranking, we find countries like Brazil, India, and Russia, with scores of 24.7, 28.7, and 22.1, respectively. These emerging countries face significant challenges in strengthening their innovation linkages. While they have great potential in terms of population and natural resources, the lack of advanced infrastructure, governance problems, and limited investment in research constrain their ability to create strong connections among the various actors in the innovation system. At the bottom of the ranking, we find countries like Yemen (14.3), Iraq (0.3), and Niger (1.4), reflecting situations of extreme economic and political difficulty that make it almost impossible to develop a cohesive innovation system. In these countries, the lack of political stability, infrastructure, and qualified human capital drastically limits the possibility of developing effective innovation linkages.

Innovation linkages globally between 2013 and 2022. The analysis of innovation linkages data between 2013 and 2022 reveals a highly varied landscape, with some countries making significant progress and others experiencing a drastic decline in their innovation capabilities. Among the countries with the most substantial absolute improvement, Guinea stands out with an increase of 15.6 points, representing a growth of 110.64%. This progress is remarkable, especially considering that Guinea started from a relatively low base but managed to more than double its score, indicating strong development of innovation infrastructures and significant improvement in collaboration among innovation system actors. Another country that recorded substantial growth is Uzbekistan, with an increase of 12.6 points and a percentage change of 104.13%. This improvement reflects the country's commitment to enhancing its innovation capabilities, likely through economic reforms and increased investments in research and development. Similarly, Albania saw a 103.81% increase, highlighting an acceleration of innovation activities and growing integration among different sector actors. Bulgaria, with a 77.39% increase, and Iceland, with 67.51%, demonstrate how countries with a good starting point can continue to improve their innovation linkages significantly. Iceland, in particular, has made significant progress despite its small size, likely thanks to targeted policies promoting collaboration between businesses, research institutes, and the public sector. On the other hand, the analysis also reveals worrying trends in several countries that have experienced significant declines

in their innovation scores. The most extreme case is Qatar, which saw a decrease of 53 points, corresponding to a drop of 65.43%. This dramatic decline suggests a severe weakening of the country's innovation networks, possibly due to factors such as economic instability, reduced investments in research and development, or decreased international cooperation. A similar trend is observed in other countries like Panama and Burkina Faso, which recorded declines of 62.40% and 60.43%, respectively. These data indicate a significant erosion of innovation capabilities, which could be linked to economic crises, political instability, or disinvestment in key sectors. Countries like Jordan and North Macedonia also show worrying declines, with reductions of 31.20% and 56.71%, respectively. These data suggest that these countries may have encountered difficulties in maintaining and developing their innovation networks, possibly due to a lack of continuity in innovation support policies or socio-political instability that has undermined collaboration among system actors. Italy, while having recorded a modest increase of 18.75%, is in an intermediate position. This suggests that despite progress, the country continues to face structural challenges that limit the full realization of its innovation potential. The growth is positive, but not sufficient to keep pace with more dynamic countries. Countries like China, which increased its innovation linkages by 31.90%, and Sweden, with a 37.15% increase, demonstrate that substantial investments in research and development and a strong commitment to international collaboration can lead to significant improvements. China, in particular, is benefiting from a massive push towards innovation, supported by favorable government policies and a rapidly expanding domestic market that facilitates the creation of increasingly strong innovation networks. Overall, the data shows a clear division between countries that have been able to capitalize on effective innovation promotion policies and those that have seen a deterioration in their capabilities in this sector. The countries that have achieved the best performances tend to be those that have implemented stable and consistent policies over time, investing in education, technological infrastructure, and promoting cooperation between the public and private sectors. Conversely, the countries that have experienced the most significant declines in innovation scores are often those characterized by economic or political instability or that have undergone significant cuts in funding for research and development. Qatar's case is emblematic, showing how a country that had achieved a high level of innovation linkages can quickly lose ground if it fails to sustain and adapt its innovation ecosystem to changing global economic conditions. This underscores the importance of economic policies that are not only ambitious but also resilient and capable of adapting to emerging challenges. The United Arab Emirates, with a 16.70% decrease, also represents an example of how success in innovation requires not only resources but also a flexible and sustainable system that can adapt to new needs. This decline could be a warning sign for other countries that are investing heavily in infrastructure without developing an equally solid and integrated innovation ecosystem.

Economic policies to promote innovation linkages. Economic policies to promote innovation linkages must be carefully designed to strengthen integration and collaboration among various actors in the innovation system, including businesses, universities, research centers, government institutions, and civil society organizations. A crucial element is investment in human capital, which requires not only high-quality education but also the promotion of skills specifically related to innovation and the ability to work in multidisciplinary teams. This can be achieved through continuous training programs and research incentives aimed at stimulating the development of advanced skills in STEM disciplines (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics), as well as in areas such as innovation management, intellectual property, and entrepreneurship. In parallel, it is essential to strengthen the mechanisms for technology transfer between universities and businesses, facilitating the transfer of knowledge and technologies from academia to the productive sector. This can be achieved by

establishing technology transfer offices in universities and offering tax incentives for businesses that collaborate with research institutions. These offices can act as intermediaries, helping to translate academic research results into concrete commercial applications, thereby facilitating the creation of new innovative products and services. Another critical area is the development of advanced technological infrastructures, such as joint research laboratories and technology parks, which offer shared spaces and resources for collaboration among researchers, engineers, and entrepreneurs. These innovation hubs not only provide access to cutting-edge technologies but also foster an environment where ideas and skills can be freely exchanged, thus promoting the emergence of new entrepreneurial initiatives. It is essential that these spaces are accessible to a wide range of actors, including small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which often have limited resources to independently invest in research and development infrastructure. Financial incentives, such as grants and tax breaks, can be used to encourage SMEs to actively participate in innovation networks, collaborating with universities and large companies in joint research projects. The role of the government is also crucial in promoting a regulatory and legislative framework that supports innovation and collaboration. This includes simplifying bureaucratic procedures for creating innovative enterprises and reducing legal barriers that hinder public-private cooperation. Regulatory reforms should aim to create a more favorable environment for knowledge sharing and the adoption of new technologies, while ensuring the protection of intellectual property rights. Moreover, it is essential to develop support policies that encourage the mobility of researchers and professionals among universities, research centers, and businesses, thereby facilitating the exchange of ideas and skills. The creation of exchange programs and scholarships for researchers and entrepreneurs can stimulate knowledge transfer and networking, helping to strengthen innovation linkages at the national and international levels. In parallel, economic policies should incentivize the creation of industrial clusters and business networks, where companies operating in similar or complementary sectors can collaborate on innovation projects. These clusters can promote technological specialization and production efficiency, enhancing global competitiveness. Governments can support these efforts by providing shared infrastructure, such as research and development centers and well-equipped laboratories, as well as offering specific funding programs for companies participating in collaborative projects. Moreover, promoting the internationalization of innovation networks is crucial for integrating local markets into global flows of knowledge and technology. Participation in international research and development networks, access to foreign markets, and collaboration with international partners can expand innovation opportunities and improve the competitiveness of national businesses. Another essential component of policies to promote innovation linkages is support for a culture of entrepreneurship and open innovation. This involves not only promoting entrepreneurial initiatives but also creating an environment where ideas can be shared and developed collaboratively. Governments can incentivize open innovation through digital platforms that facilitate the sharing of ideas, projects, and resources among various actors, including citizens, universities, businesses, and public institutions. These platforms can act as catalysts for innovation, allowing a broad spectrum of participants to contribute with skills and innovative ideas, thus creating a more inclusive and dynamic innovation ecosystem. Moreover, entrepreneurial training programs and startup accelerators can help new entrepreneurs develop crucial innovation skills, from business management to capital raising, thus promoting a new generation of innovation leaders. Economic policies should also focus on including traditional sectors and civil society in innovation processes. Innovation should not be limited to advanced technology sectors but should permeate all areas of the economy and society. Engaging agriculture, manufacturing, services, and local communities in innovation projects can generate more sustainable and resilient solutions. Regional development programs, which integrate local specificities with opportunities offered by international collaboration, can help create innovation linkages that respond to the real needs of communities while reducing territorial disparities. This inclusive approach to

innovation can be supported through specific incentives for projects involving partnerships between businesses, non-governmental organizations, and local communities, thus promoting more balanced and sustainable economic development. Finally, environmental sustainability must be a central driver in economic policies aimed at promoting innovation linkages. The challenges related to climate change and the management of natural resources offer significant opportunities to develop new sustainable technologies and practices. Governments can incentivize sustainable innovation through tax breaks, funding for research in renewable energy and green technologies, and regulations that encourage emission reductions and energy efficiency. Moreover, promoting smart cities and adopting technologies for the sustainable management of urban resources can create new innovation linkages among the public sector, private sector, and local communities, contributing to a more sustainable and innovative future. The transition to a green economy not only improves innovation linkages but can also strengthen a country's global competitiveness, positioning it as a leader in future technologies.

Conclusions. The value of innovation linkages has decreased on average by 1.09% for the countries considered between 2013 and 2022. There are countries where the value of innovation linkages has significantly increased between 2013 and 2022, such as Guinea with +110.64%, Uzbekistan with +104.13%, Albania with +103.81%, Bulgaria with +77.39%, and Iceland with +67.51%. However, there are also countries where the value of innovation linkages has significantly decreased, such as Guatemala with -57.49%, Mozambique with -58.71%, Burkina Faso with -60.43%, Panama with -62.40%, and Qatar with -65.43%.

Country	2022	Country	2022	Country	2022
Israel	78,4	Qatar	28	Namibia	20,6
Sweden	68,3	Indonesia	27,4	Morocco	20,5
Finland	66,4	Rwanda	26,9	Philippines	20,5
United States	66	Vietnam	26,8	Romania	20,1
Switzerland	64,3	Tanzania	26,4	Burundi	19,9
Canada	59,8	Oman	26,2	Mexico	19,9
Iceland	59,8	South Africa	26,1	Panama	19,7
Austria	57,5	Ghana	25,7	Zimbabwe	19,6
Belgium	55,9	Botswana	25,4	Peru	19,4
Singapore	54,3	Kenya	25,4	Benin	19,3
Netherlands	53,7	Greece	25,1	Bangladesh	19,1
Denmark	53,1	Azerbaijan	24,9	Paraguay	19,1
Germany	52,2	Brazil	24,7	Senegal	18,9
United Kingdom	52	Croatia	24,7	Madagascar	18,7
Luxembourg	50,1	Uzbekistan	24,7	Nepal	18,6
Australia	48	Pakistan	24,6	Trinidad and Tobago	18,6
United Arab Emirates	47,9	Lao PDR	24,5	Argentina	18,4
Korea, Rep.	47,9	Egypt, Arab Rep.	24,3	Nigeria	18,3
Norway	47,9	Sri Lanka	23,4	Iran, Islamic Rep.	18,1
Japan	47,7	Mali	23,4	Ethiopia	17,9
Malta	47	Thailand	23,4	Mauritania	17,9
Ireland	45,5	Poland	23	Guatemala	17,6
Czechia	45,4	Brunei Darussalam	22,9	Algeria	17,4

Hong Kong SAR, China	44,1	Georgia	22,8	Armenia	17,2
France	41,8	Slovak Republic	22,3	North Macedonia	17,1
Cyprus	41	Dominican Republic	22,1	Burkina Faso	16,5
Italy	39,9	Russian Federation	22,1	Tunisia	16,5
New Zealand	37,8	Zambia	22,1	Moldova	16,3
Estonia	37,7	Serbia	22	Tajikistan	16,1
China	36,8	Kuwait	21,6	Honduras	16
Slovenia	36,8	Turkiye	21,5	Mongolia	15,4
Bulgaria	35,3	Albania	21,4	Bosnia and Herzegovina	15,3
Saudi Arabia	33,9	Chile	21,3	Ecuador	15,3
Lithuania	33,8	Cameroon	21,3	Nicaragua	14,9
Jordan	32,2	Ukraine	21,3	Kazakhstan	14,3
Latvia	31,9	Cote d'Ivoire	21,2	Yemen, Rep.	14,3
Malaysia	31,2	Colombia	21,2	Kyrgyz Republic	13,7
Portugal	30,6	Costa Rica	21,2	El Salvador	13,7
Guinea	29,7	Mozambique	21,1	Angola	12,1
Spain	29,6	Cambodia	20,9	Myanmar	11,4
Bahrain	29,3	Montenegro	20,7	Belarus	6,8
Hungary	29	Uganda	20,7	Togo	2,8
India	28,7	Uruguay	20,7	Niger	1,4
Jamaica	28,5	Mauritius	20,6	Iraq	0,3

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